

Rural Assessment Administration as a Response to Educational Support Stagnation

Between 1988 and 1993 in British Columbia, there were several changes to the class size and composition language in various district collective agreements. Some local agreements included successful class cap sizes, such as SD61, 82, 68, and 36. School districts 39 and 68 were both part of the 1991 strike that sought better classroom conditions.

Efficient classroom conditions are the hallmark of any stable and beneficial classroom; the output of students is directly correlated to their ability to learn and apply knowledge, which stems from an emotionally healthy and physically safe learning environment (Kweon et al., 2017).

There is existing research that ties together the importance of children's prosocial behaviour at the beginning of the school year, resulting in lowering depressive symptoms during the school year, and leading to improved academic achievement at the end of the school year (Oberle et al., 2023).

Prosocial behaviours, identified by Oberle et al. as being "[. . .] associated with social, emotional, and psychological benefits in childhood and adolescence" (pp. 633). Reasonably, a positive association with peers will generally elicit a positive mindset. It stands to reason that for effective, positive relationships to emerge and foster, a positive classroom must be provided as a physical environment in which students can connect, grow, and participate.

Yet British Columbia has seen a downward spiral in emotional health in youth in the past decade (Oberle et al., 2025). There is data to suggest that due to increasing demands upon teachers without additional support, classrooms are not as positive as in the past due to factors that include fewer educational assistants (EAs), bigger class sizes, and fewer mental health supports (both in district and on-site). While more social-emotional knowledge for students is helpful for them to prosper and grow in class and amongst their peers (Oberle et al., 2023), there is little being done to assist teachers in providing tools to create this environment.

One particularly concerning factor of addressing overall classroom health is the difficulty in getting appropriate diagnoses for students with neurodevelopmental disorders and behavioural disorders.

Historically, teachers have had varying levels of support for coded students, but the last decade has seen a drop in student support for diagnoses, as well as increasing challenges for access to psychological and medical assessments. The outcome is teachers having to teach in classrooms that are far beyond beneficial teacher-student ratios, as well as having to address student behaviours that are disruptive and often violent, while still trying to maintain a positive learning environment.

The effect of this is a higher burnout rate for teachers and a lower quality learning environment for students. A 2024 British Columbia Teachers Federation survey published that close to 60% of teachers report an unmanageable workload (BCTF).

Trauma from a negative classroom can result in poor teacher retention rates, emotionally distressed educators, and a field where it is more difficult to recruit knowledgeable teachers for students. Waiting lists for

One potential resolution to some of the classroom composition issues is the ease of obtaining assessments. Students identified as likely needing a psychological assessment should have an easier method of obtaining a psychometric evaluation or assessment, particularly rural students. This would provide a faster pathway to accessing classroom supports, as students with a designation are given varying levels of assistance depending on their designation. Currently, wait times for assessments are extreme. According to Autism BC, waitlists for publicly supported autism diagnostic paths (via the BC Autism Assessment Network, BCAAN) typically average 80.6 weeks (AutismBC). The outcome of such long wait times is that without a diagnosis, the child struggles in school, and the teacher is unable to meet the child's specific needs because supports are not in place due to not being coded. Additionally, students who live in rural areas are at an extreme disadvantage, as travel costs and travel times can be restrictive to accessing resources. The government publishes the provincial average wait time for ADHD evaluations; diagnoses are frequently made by pediatricians or psychiatrists, who also have long waitlists. When relying on public referrals, AutismBC and ADHD stakeholder reports highlight waitlists of more than 1.5 years for evaluations (Union of BC Municipalities).

The reality for rural families is even more dire. Disparities noted by the Union of BC Municipalities note that *extended wait times* and challenges with recruitment and retention have made it difficult to offer timely neurodevelopmental assessment access across regions (Northern Health and Island Health included).

Having a rural assessment initiative would allow students to access the diagnostic resources in a more timely manner, allowing their district to apply for funding for in-class supports. A pathway to reaching this goal would be to have the provincial government create a resources team of several clinicians: a physician (on or off-site), a registered clinical psychologist, and two to three Level B psychometric administrators. A training program for psychometric tests would need to be given to the Level B test administrators, who could begin with lower-level testing where needed and have regular discussions with the registered psychologist for any Level C tests. A physician, in connection with the team, could take the psychologist's recommendations for diagnoses and administer any required physical examinations. Even five of these rural centres would be a benefit to rural communities, who could avoid travel and its expenditures to larger centres and help students and families reach support they need.

Works Cited

AutismBC. (2022, November). *What we've heard: Feedback on family connection centres (FCCs) and the CYSN framework*. |

<https://www.autismbc.ca/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/FCC-Report-2022.pdf>

British Columbia Teachers' Federation. (2024, May). *BCTF membership survey summary report 2023–24*.

https://www.bctf.ca/docs/default-source/for-news-and-stories/bctf-membership-survey-summary-report-2023-2024.pdf?sfvrsn=3bdb986c_2

Kweon, B. S., Ellis, C. D., Lee, J., & Jacobs, K. (2017). The link between school environments and student academic performance. *Urban forestry & urban greening*, 23, 35-43.

Oberle, E., Ji, X. R., & Molyneux, T. M. (2023). Pathways from prosocial behaviour to emotional health and academic achievement in early adolescence. *The Journal of Early Adolescence*, 43(5), 632-653.

Oberle, E., Ji, X. R., Molyneux, T., Guhn, M., Forer, B., Thomson, K., ... & Gadermann, A. (2025). | Mental Well-being Trends and School-based Protective Factors among Adolescents in British Columbia (2015 to 2022): A Population-Based Study. *Social Science & Medicine*, 118201.

Union of BC Municipalities. (2022). *Reducing neurodevelopment assessment wait times* (Resolution No. 2022-EB42).

<https://www.ubcm.ca/convention-resolutions/resolutions/resolutions-database/reducing-neurodevelopment-assessment-wait>